

The Catalytic Effect of Aluminium Ions added to Cupric Oxide Catalyst during Propan-2-ol Decomposition

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Manuscript received 17 July 1985, accepted 17 January 1986

The acid base solid, $\text{CuO-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, was examined as a potential catalyst for decomposition of propan-2-ol. The high dehydrogenation activity occurred for pure CuO at lower calcination temperature is related to the presence of basic active chemisorbed oxygen. Addition of Al^{+++} ions in lower concentrations causes variation of either Fermi level and/or the oxidation-reduction state of the copper ions. At higher Al^{+++} ions concentration, the solid solution formed varies the specificity of the surface towards the dehydrogenation-dehydration processes.

CUPRIC oxide has attracted considerable attention due to its industrial applications^{1,2} and for fundamental understanding of catalyst activation³. Chemisorption of oxygen on copper oxide was studied and the process was visualised as an expansion of the lattice to incorporate the adsorbed oxygen creating vacancies⁴. Hence, a localised layer of negative charge is generated on the catalyst surface. Catalytic interaction of organic substances over its surface was carried out effectively. An increase of methanol conversion rate was produced over supported CuO where it was suggested that CuO was dispersed over the Al_2O_3 support⁵. XRD investigations of such material reveals the presence of Cu_2O peak as a second phase⁶. This is also was a result of the work carried out using copper containing zeolite by TPR⁷.

This article examines the catalytic influence of Al^{+++} ions either doped or mixed with CuO catalyst. Study of propan-2-ol decomposition was selected as a test reaction for the surface acid-base properties change over the surface.

Experimental

Catalysts were prepared by impregnating copper carbonate (A.R.) with $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution in molar ratios of 0.5 upto 50 mol %. The parent materials were dried at 110° and subsequently calcined at different temperatures from 200 upto 700° in a flow of dry air.

The decomposition of propan-2-ol was performed in a conventional flow apparatus operated at atmospheric pressure. The apparatus used in this study was described previously⁸. For most runs, 0.5 g of catalyst was used diluted with quartz grains of uniform size. The total flow of N_2 gas was 400 ml (NTP) min^{-1} charged with 2.2% reactant of

alcohol. Analysis were carried out with a PYE Unicam 104 flame ionisation detector (FID). The column (1/8" o.d $\times$ 1.5 m) was PEG 20% filled with 60-80 mesh celite. In the exit-feed, acetone and propylene were detected as the only products of the catalytic experiments together with the unreacted alcohol. The accuracy of the analytical procedure used was within 5% on the basis of carbon material balance. The experimental results presented are not influenced by heat transport or diffusion limitation effects.

Results

Typical experimental results obtained with CuO calcined at 400° for 2 h at different reaction temperatures are given in Fig. 1. The catalyst flow rate ratio was 0.467 g cat/mol/l/h. Based on these data, two main processes taking place over the catalyst surface were (a) the dehydrogenation reaction where acetone was produced with a high % yield at low catalytic reaction temperature and (b) increasing the catalytic temperature, the dehydration process commenced at 200° and reached its maximum at 300°. Also, it appears that the total conversion was 60% at 200° while it decreases monotonously reaching a minimum at 400°. Noticing the variation of % conversion with the catalytic reaction temperature, it appears that from 200 upto 400° it is only 10% less. Consequently, it can be predicted that the dehydration reaction takes place at the expense of the dehydrogenation process.

The lattice nature of the solid catalysts was tested measuring its catalytic activity parameters against the calcination temperature. Fig. 2 indicates the surface property variation. At 300 and 400°, it seems that the surface has catalytic capacity towards dehydrogenation as well as dehydration

Fig 1. Decomposition activity of CuO catalyst for propan-2-ol at different reaction temperatures: (●) conversion of propan-2-ol, (○) yield of acetone and (×) yield of propylene

Fig 2. Activity of CuO catalysts for propan-2-ol decomposition calcined at different temperatures for 2 h. (●) conversion of propan-2-ol, (○) yield of acetone and (×) yield of propylene

processes. After that temperatures, a large deviation occurred. The catalyst calcined at 700° has mainly dehydrogenation activity. These data indicate that different active sites are playing role over the surface as the calcination temperature develops.

The nature of the pores was tested for catalyst calcined at 400° using Wheeler's treatment⁹ where effectiveness of the pores was calculated and showed no retardation effect on the catalytic process, i.e. the decomposition reaction is only influenced by the surface property.

Table 1 gives the experimental results of W/F values as a function of % conversion. It appears that on increasing W/F value the conversion increases.

The presence of Al⁺⁺⁺ ions in CuO matrix was studied under the same experimental conditions as in case of the pure catalyst. Fig. 3. describes the variation of % conversion yield of either acetone or propylene. At 0.5 mole % Al⁺⁺⁺ ions, the % conversion decreases. Adopting mechanism of

Fig 3. Effect of Al⁺⁺⁺ ions doped and mixed with CuO catalyst calcined at 500° for 2 h for propan-2-ol decomposition. (●) conversion of propan-2-ol, (○) yield of acetone and (×) yield of propylene.

TABLE 1—% CONVERSION, YIELD AND SELECTIVITY ON CuO CATALYST CALCINED AT 400° FOR 2 h FOR DECOMPOSITION OF PROPAN-2-OL

W/F	% Conv	% Yield		% Selectivity	
		Acetone	Propylene	Acetone	Propylene
0.093	28.68	11.30	10.00	39.40	34.87
0.280	45.74	22.38	17.63	48.93	38.54
0.467	54.67	28.79	22.70	52.66	41.52
0.653	58.14	32.50	24.73	55.90	42.54
0.933	61.22	34.50	26.50	56.35	43.29

Fig. 4. Decomposition of propan-2-ol over CuO doped with 0.5 mol % Al^{3+} ions calcined at different temperatures for 2 h: (●) conversion of propan-2-ol, (○) yield of acetone and (×) yield of propylene.

Fig. 5. Decomposition of propan-2-ol over CuO mixed with 50 mol % Al^{3+} ions calcined at different temperatures: (●) conversion of propan-2-ol, (○) yield of acetone and (×) yield of propylene.

doping, as will be discussed later, consumption of the available active sites for propan-2-ol chemisorption decreases leading to low % conversion. Increasing Al^{3+} ion concentration, the conversion increases reaching a maximum at 1 mol % and then gradually decreases. Further increase to 5 mol %, lead to a sudden drop for % acetone and an increase of % propylene. This phenomenon could be attributed to the increase of defects upto 1 mol %, At 5 mol %, the commencement of solid solution of copper aluminate starts, its property seems to be

different than those of the individual oxides. Further formation of spinel structure leading to an enhancement of the dehydrogenation which occurs at the expense of the dehydration process.

The catalytic experiments conducted using catalysts contain either 0.5 or 50 mol % Al^{3+} ions, were carried out to determine the difference between doping effect and solid solution formation over the catalyst surface. Figs. 4 and 5 illustrate these differences. A pronounced effect was found using $CuO + 0.5$ mol % Al^{3+} ions where both processes are taking place, while with $CuO + 50$ mol % Al^{3+} ion catalyst, the surface has entirely dehydrogenation activity.

Discussion

The results show that when the kinetics of a catalytic reaction are complex or unknown, the catalysts studied have to be compared at similar W/F values otherwise interpretation of the experimental results may be misleading.

One of the factors to control the activity in the decomposition of alcohols is the acid-base properties of the catalyst surface¹⁰. With acidic catalysts, the dehydrogenation predominantly takes place, while, over basic catalysts the dehydration reaction proceeds. Changes in their rate ratios will consequently attribute to the change in the acidic and basic centers activity.

For pure CuO catalyst, the most predominant change in the activity occurred at 200° , where the catalyst will tend to catalyse the dehydrogenation process. At higher catalytic temperature both reactions proceeded. This can be visualised on the basis of the experimental results of Gunningham *et al.*¹¹, that at 200° , more basic centers exist due to the oxygen chemisorption, adopting the following mechanism,

The change in the catalytic centers over the surface is illustrated in Fig. 2, where the effect of the catalyst backing temperature varied. A promiscuous nature of the surface appeared at calcination temperature of 300° . At 600° calcination temperature, a wide variation occurs where propylene will be produced at the expense of acetone yield. Previous work¹² has detected surface chemisorbed oxygen for catalysts calcined at lower rather higher temperatures. This phenomenon can support the idea that the oxygen chemisorbed can act as a dehydrogenation center specially for catalysts calcined at lower temperature and used at lower catalytic reaction temperatures.

Admission of Al_2O_3 into CuO matrix affects CuO catalytic properties in such a way that when Al^{3+} ion has low concentration, the surface acts as dehydrogenation and dehydration catalyst. While, when Al^{3+} ion reaches 50 mol %, the

activity polarises mainly to dehydrogenation reaction. It is obvious that there are several parameters that influence the catalytic activity. One of the most important factors, is the position of the Fermi level at the surface of the metal oxide^{13,14} by which the charge transfer between the surface and alcohol molecules plays the dominant rate determining step; also, the oxidation-reduction reaction of metal oxide surface and the relative position and availability of the reaction sites on the surface where propan-2-ol dehydrogenation is structure sensitive.

Therefore, it could be believed that Al^{III} ions in lower concentrations can cause the variation of either the Fermi level and the oxidation-reduction state of the surface via the following mechanism,

This mechanism will hinder the amount of propan-2-ol chemisorbed and is in accordance with the experimental results of CuO catalyst doped with 0.5 mol % Al^{III} ions. On increasing of Al^{III} ion concentrations, the acidic nature of the surface increases due to the Lewis acid sites induction. This in its turn affects the % conversion where a maximum was obtained when 1 mol % Al^{III}

ion was admitted. More Al^{III} ion will form CuAl₂O₄, its concentration will affect either the % conversion of the specificity of the surface towards the reaction process type.

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